

Primary School-Based Support Teams' Experiences And Practices When Supporting Teachers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : School-Based Support Team, District Based Support Team, Inclusive Education, barriers to learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6323544</p>	<p><i>School-Based Support Teams play a key role in providing support to teachers and learners through early identification and intervention to learners experiencing barriers to learning. This study investigates School-Based Support Teams experiences of the nature of support they provided to schools. An interpretivism paradigm, qualitative approach was adopted. A non-probability sampling method of purposive sampling was used to select participants from School-Based Support Team members from six public schools in King Cetshwayo District. Data for this study were collected during six focus group interviews which resulted in the generation of fifteen themes including: the School-Based Support Teams understanding of Inclusive Education in White Paper 6, establishment and functionality of School-Based Support Teams especially with regards to providing support within their schools, their own experiences in serving as School-Based Support Team, challenges they experience in teaching learners experiencing barriers to learning and the kind of support they require as School-Based Support Team members to improve their functionality. The findings revealed that despite the implementation of Inclusive Education, there are still gaps. The study recommends that: educators be supported through conducting ongoing capacity building to equip them with skills needed, and the District-Based Support Team should provide comprehensive support and closely monitor School-Based Support Teams.</i></p>

Introduction

Engelbrecht (2006) states that the most striking thing which sets South Africa (SA) apart from many other countries is the way in which it delivered education to the masses. It was based on deeply biased racial attitudes and institutional practices that discriminated against race groups and led to a deeply entrenched sense of disintegration and disparity that has created a ripple effect throughout society and education as a microcosym.

The Education for All (EFA) initiative marked a global movement towards providing quality basic education to all children, youth and adults (UNESCO, 1990). In response to the Salamanca Statement and Framework on Special Needs Education, the South African government promulgated Acts and Policies promoting the inclusion of learners with special needs in education (UNESCO, 1994). SA's National Curriculum Statement (NCS) (DoE, 2002), was introduced supporting and encapsulating the principles of social justice, human rights, healthy needs environment and inclusivity (Theron, 2016). The Education White Paper 6: Building an Inclusive Education and Training Systems (EWP6) (DoE, 2001), was formulated as a response to the inequalities that existed during apartheid and was thus an attempt to redress the imbalances of the past and focuses mainly on building a caring and supportive school environment and minimising barriers to teaching, learning and development, emphasising the strengthening of education support services to minimise potential barriers to learning. To realise its objectives of strengthening education support services it established District-Based Support Teams (DBST) and School-Based Support Teams (SBST) (Wenner& Campbell ,2017).

According to EWP6 (DoE, 2001), the DBST is a team comprising of departmental professionals whose role is to promote IE through training, curriculum delivery, distribution of resources, identification, assessments and to address barriers to learning leadership and general management. While the primary roles of the DBST, on the one hand, is to evaluate programmes, diagnose their effectiveness and suggest modifications, the SBST. On the other hand, it is a support team with mandate to coordinate learner and teacher support services by identifying and addressing the needs of not only the learner but also the teacher and the institution (DoE, 2001). South Africa, undeniably, has some of the best policies and plans in place to address the issue of IE.

The following policy frameworks address issues of IE: the Constitution of the Republic of SA (Act 108 of 1996) (RSA, 1996) lays the foundation for the development of education; the Bill of Rights (Section 28) ensures that

every child has a right to basic education, social care and protection from mistreatment, neglect, abuse and degradation (RSA, 1996); The South African Schools (Act 84 of 1996) stresses the need for all public schools to provide equal education to all learners and to admit learners regardless of their educational requirements without unfairly discriminating against them (DoE, 1996); the Children's Act (38 of 2005) does not only set out the principles relating to the care and protection of children but also defines parental responsibilities and the DoE's draft policy on Screening, Identification, Assessment and Support (SIAS) (DoE, 2014), provides a policy framework for the standardisation of the procedures to identify, assess and provide learning support programmes for all learners requiring additional support to enhance their participation and inclusion.

Implementation of IE in SA requires well-planned districts as well as school-level support services and is about more than just accepting learners with different needs in mainstream schools (Mahlo & Hugo 2013). Administratively, the principal steers the SBST and the entire team, which includes the Deputy Principal or Head of Department as the chairperson of the committee and teachers as additional members. The number of members in a team depends on the size of the school. Preference is given to teachers with psychology or special education in their qualifications, life orientation, or any teachers with a passion or positive attitude in dealing with learner welfare. The DoE needs to be aware of the challenges faced by SBST members when performing their assigned duties.

At-risk and vulnerable learners need special intervention and a nurturing environment where they feel safe and wanted. A support programme is a planned reaction towards an identified need for achievement, making a positive contribution to the overall student experience and output rates (Kerzner, 2017). Barr and Keating (1985), define a support programme as a planned response towards an identified need for action and support programmes can enhance academic performance and positively contribute to the overall student's experience and throughput rates (Agar and Knopfmacher, 1995).

The motivation for engaging in this study is based on a need to emphasise early identification and intervention of learners with barriers to learning and to provide support to teachers in terms of capacity building. The researchers noted, while working at schools, that although SBSTs had been established; in most schools they are dysfunctional due to a variety of reasons. Early identification of learners with barriers to learning is still a challenge in some schools and SBSTs are struggling to identify and refer learners timeously. Often the SBST can do little in terms of intervention. Based on the high rate of psycho-educational and psycho-social issues, the researchers conducted this study on school-based support teams' experiences and practices and the researchers tackled the following issues:

- What are the experiences of primary school SBST's?
- What challenges do primary school SBST's face?
- What type of support do primary school SBST's need to improve their functionality?

Theoretical framework

The study derived its framework from Bronfenbrenner's (1979), ecological systems theory (EST), a multidimensional model of human development. It suggests that there are levels of interacting systems resulting in change, growth and development such as physical, psychological, biological, social and cultural (Kruger & Swart 2010). What happens in one system affects and is affected by other systems. Bronfenbrenner described five systems that influence development: Micro-system, Meso-system, Exo-system, Macro-system and Chrono-system (Bronfenbrenner, 2005). A SBST is closest to the child and their needs and plays an active role in the identification thereof and provides support. If the SBST fails to perform its role as expected, the schools will likely continue to have over-aged learners, poor performance and other social issues. Learners might experience challenges and are at risk of dropping out of school. Ecological systems theory (EST) outlines the importance of a support system for individual learners.

Figure 1: Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (Vélez-Agosto, 2017)

In a study of social inclusion and participation of young people with dual sensory impairment in mainstream schools, Kamenopoulou (2012), employed EST to explore the extent that young people were socially included in the mainstream environment and to identify any barriers to their participation. Thus, using EST as the theoretical framework for the study, the mainstream school is perceived as a system whose components continuously interact and influence social inclusion. This view finds support in Llewellyn and Hogan's (2000), argument that EST can be useful in naturalistic case study research on disability whose aim is to explore development about real-life contexts.

Mahlo and Hugo (2013) in Gauteng discovered that the environment plays an active role during the implementation of IE in the foundation phase, with both learners and teachers. If the systems do not work together (support each other) then the vision of IE will not be realised. There is an interconnection between schools, districts, provinces and national education and if SBST's are working closely with the schools and the district, learners are more likely to reach their highest potential and succeed, ultimately benefiting the country. However, the contrary is also true; for example, if a learner is experiencing barriers to learning, does not receive help at school, they will probably drop out and become unemployable because of lack of skills. Ecological systems theory acknowledges the vision of IE as it emphasises the full development of learners.

Literature review

According to WHO (2012), disability arises from the interaction between an impairment, in a person's body, function or structure, and the society (systems) in which that person lives. Many countries struggle with bringing IE policies into practice and to successfully implement inclusion. Teachers must have adequate training, sufficient support and positive attitudes (Frankel, Gold & Ajodhia-Andrews, 2010). The primary explanation for lack of any significant movement on inclusive policy is the apparent lack of clarity in the policy as well as issues pertaining to the poor implementation of this policy.

In Salamanca, Spain governments and international organisations met to further the objective of Education for All by considering fundamental policy shifts required to promote IE by enabling schools to serve all children, particularly those with special education needs. The Salamanca Statement explains that the focus should not be on changing the learner to fit into the education system, but to changing the system to fit the learners' needs (UNESCO, 1994).

A study in Australia (Milton & Forlin, 2003) revealed that the role of support has taken on a personal element examining a school's effectiveness in implementing IE, such as attitudes of school staff, students, parents and community. Teachers are concerned about their competence in supporting learners and managed to overcome challenges through the concerted efforts of all stakeholders. Regardless of financial support, teachers and support teams value the incorporation of diversity and are prepared to commit to facilitating the process.

Australian systems, schools and communities are taking a pro-active and positive approach towards establishing more inclusive school communities.

Another international study conducted by Hauwadhanasuk, Zhuang, Everson, Yu and Karnas (2019) in China, Turkey and Thailand mention practices and challenges. The similarities revealed that the governments have been proactive and approve that educational programs and supports are implemented. Hauwadhanasuk et al., (2019) show that teachers lack knowledge of special education and have insufficient training and behavioural management skills to teach learners with disabilities and teachers were found to lack skills to construct assessment tools. They suggest that departmental officials, in all three countries, should establish in-service professional training programmes; as well as developmental research programs on special education and IE.

Further research conducted in Botswana (Rampana, 2015), on the effectiveness of School Intervention Teams (SITs) in assisting learners with special education needs revealed that the effectiveness of SITs depends on the positive attitude and support by the School Management Team (SMT), parents, teachers and stakeholders. There is a gap between recommendation and implementation of IE and it hinders the proper functioning of SITs.

EWP6 (DoE, 2001) asserts that the Department of Education (DoE) carries a special responsibility to ensure that all learners, regardless of their level of ability, should have access to education in order to achieve their potential and outlines a national strategy for systematically addressing and removing barriers to learning through: establishing full-service schools (FSS), converting special schools into resource centres, training education managers and teachers, developing institutional and district support structures, and pursuing a funding strategy. The creation of multi-level support teams – at the school, district, and special school levels (full-service schools and resource centres) – to provide support, for learners with special needs, in teaching, learning and assessment was outlined in EWP6. EWP6 outlined the government's policies for a single, undivided education system for all learners, including those with disabilities, in the hope that IE would create a more unified and compassionate society. This White Paper was designed to transform the South African education system by building an integrated system for all learners, hoping to eliminate special and ordinary schools; using a more flexible curriculum, that is suitable to the needs and abilities of learners; developing DBST's and SBST's to provide systemic support for any and all teachers who need it; and strengthening the skill of teachers to cope with more diverse classes (Muthukrishna&Schoeman, 2000).

Donohue and Bornman (2014) explain that although the practice of IE is encouraged globally, practically, what transpires on paper is a very different story. The true success of IE lies in the attitudes of the school principals. If the school principal embraces and supports IE, it is easier for the rest of the school personnel to support inclusion. According to Bornman and Donohue (2014) it is not just the negative attitudes toward disability that contributes to the complete sense of confusion towards IE on the part of South African schools but also the lack of support and resources. Oswald and Swart (2011) found that accommodating diverse learners in South African classrooms is in line with the social model of disability that views disability centrally as a social construct created by an ability-oriented environment. Disability, in this sense, sees the problem as located not in the individual, but in a societal, economic, political system and culture that fails to meet the needs of individuals (McEwan & Butler, 2007). Failure to successfully implement an IE system can be ascribed to various factors, including; (a) the failure to develop fully-inclusive schools and special schools as resource centres; (b) failure to integrate learners with learning barriers into ordinary schools; (c) lack of teaching and learning support; (d) lack of SBSTs; and the lack of trained teachers (DoE, 2001).

Although the term inclusion has become a buzzword locally and internationally, inclusion has different meanings for different people. The commonalities which run across all definitions is that it includes broad principles such as dedication to building a more democratic society, a more equitable and quality education system, a belief that extends the responsibility of regular schools to accommodate diverse learning needs for all learners (Kruger & Swart, 2010). What is underlined here is the interaction between an individual's use of a conceptual tool for understanding classrooms, teacher's practices, schools and families by viewing them as a system in themselves and interaction with the broader social context (Donald, Lazarus & Lolwana, 2010). The SBST seeks to provide support by minimising barriers to learning and improving academic performance. Wellness of learners is important in developing emotional, cognitive, physical and occupational fitness. Families, teachers, the Department of Education and other key role players in education must play their role by accommodating everyone to promote inclusion. Every learner must feel comfortable and benefit from learning. Principals must support the SBST; because if not supported, it will be dysfunctional and will be meaningless.

Research on SBST's understanding and experiences of IE in the Western Cape by Rulwa-Mnatwana (2014), revealed that SBST's are doing good work; however, they should be sustained and allowed to provide support in ways that work within their capability and broader socio-cultural context. The SBST should, as a matter of necessity, be constituted to comprise mainly of teachers, parents and learners and should provide a relevant teacher or parent with training and support, in relation to specific curriculum development projects (Landsberg et al, 2013:11).

Writing on the issue of SBST's and DBST's the Equal Education Law Centre (2016) found that both SBST's and DBST's are generally ineffective. The SBSTs in Lejweleputswa District (Lebona, 2015) was designed to identify 'at risk' learners and address barriers to learning but they lacked knowledge of policies and guidelines for IE hence the teachers, support teams and learners did not receive support from the teachers on the SBSTs. As a result, the SBSTs were unable to fulfil their purpose. DBST's were created to provide an additional layer of support to teachers in implementing and maintaining an IE system. Lebona (2015) found that the support offered by DBST's is minimal. The Equal Education Law Centre (2016) found that the lack of implementation of the IE law and policy framework is failing learners, violating their rights to basic education and equality. While significant advocacy has been underway to advance the rights of learners with learning barriers, much work still needs to be done (Disabilities in Education and IE, 2014).

Mphanda (2018) explored teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of learners with physical disabilities in South African schools and revealed different views amongst the participants on whether mainstream schools have started to assume FSS roles. Schools had not been converted to FSS for the following reasons: lack of infrastructure to accommodate learners, lack of skills, fear of negative attitudes from peers in the mainstream schools. Other findings revealed that teachers have negative attitudes towards admitting learners with physical disabilities and held misconceptions about learners living with physical disabilities and this impacted negatively on IE practices.

Education systems worldwide have provided special education and related services to students with special needs (Ryndak&Alper, 1996; Pottas, 2005) and reform in education has led to a move away from the segregation of learners with special needs in special classes toward the inclusion of learners in mainstream education. Despite new policies and curricula, this process of change has raised numerous questions about the role and responsibilities of school personnel in providing an appropriate education for all learners enrolled in mainstream schools (Daane&Beirne-Smith, 2001). As agents of change, teachers have many concerns about the implementation of IE policies (Forlin, 1995). Although legislation, conceptual and operational guidelines for the implementation of IE represents a major step forward in the transformation of the South African education system, it is often questioned whether teachers will be able to implement IE (Hay, Smit & Paulsen, 2001, 2001 cited in Pottas, 2005).

Teachers are the key element in the successful implementation of inclusive policies (Avramidis& Norwich, 2002; Swart et al., 2002; Marshall, Ralph & Palmer, 2002) and mainstream classrooms have become the primary context within which IE is to be implemented (Sands, 2000). Teachers are obliged to seek new ways to instruct all students (Brownlee & Carrington, 2000), paying special attention to the physical environment, instructional strategies, classroom management techniques, as well as educational collaboration (Voltz, Brazil, Ford & 2001). People's perceptions determine their actions (Williams & Finnegan, 2003:40) and are often directly related to learning experiences and the generalised belief systems of society (Swart et al., 2002), and has a direct influence on one's response to the world. Teachers' perceptions of inclusive policies will not only determine their acceptance of inclusive policies but will also affect their commitment to implementation (Avramidis& Norwich, 2002). A study by Conway (2017) on teachers' perspectives on learner support in a South African FSS revealed that if certain principles and practices are put in place, learners can receive full support from teachers and will be able to succeed. Teacher's attitudes towards learners with special learning needs appear to influence the type and quality of teacher-learner interactions, directly impacting on the learner's educational experiences and opportunities (Cook, 2001; Reynolds, 2001).

Teachers display a definite lack of adequate knowledge, skills and training for effective implementation of IE in SA (Hay et al., 2001) and feel unprepared and ill-equipped to teach in inclusive classrooms as a result of their lack of training, the lack of time, large classes and lack of teaching experience. According to Swart et al. (2002) fear of not being able to manage diversity resulted in feelings of hopelessness and learners being referred for assessments to specialists and placements in special programs, whilst negative attitudes and labelling resulted from misconceptions and assumptions about learners with specific educational needs

Research methodology

The study engaged the qualitative approach within the interpretive paradigm to explore primary school SBSTs experiences and practices when supporting teachers. The rationale for choosing this paradigm is that it allows for an in-depth understanding of participants' knowledge and experiences and helped researchers gain insights, discover innovative ideas and create knowledge about the SBSTs' experiences.

Participants

Non-probability sampling methods of purposive and convenience sampling were used. According to Best and Kahn (2006) purposive sampling is useful when identifying and selecting participants since they are able to provide the required information. This study chose purposive sampling because it helped the researchers to obtain valid data as the researchers received confirmation that they would only have access to schools that have SBSTs. The researchers conducted the study at six primary schools selected for purposes of data collection. One primary school was a Full-Service School, and five schools were mainstream primary schools (n=6) and were selected according to their geographic location: two schools were in urban areas, two schools were in peri-urban areas and the last two schools were in rural areas. The size of the school (total school population) determined the number of participants interviewed. Both genders received due consideration in the study, five males and 22 females. SBST participants included Principals, Deputy Principals, Heads of Department, senior teachers, co-opted members and teaching staff.

Table 1. Number of participants from each institution

SCHOOL	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
1	4
2	4
3	5
4	5
5	6
6	3
TOTAL	n=27

Method of data collection

Semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted. Each school formed a focus group. Silverman (2000) states that the purpose of the research interviews is to explore the experiences, views, beliefs and motivation of participants. An interview schedule, with questions set in a predetermined order (Bertram & Christiansen, 2015), was used as a data collection instrument which, helped guide the researchers towards the research objectives, and probe participant's responses and encourage them to provide details. The researchers sought written consent to utilise a tape-recorder ensure that all data was correctly captured. Semi-structured interview sessions were between 45 to 60 minutes and conducted in English; however, participants were given permission to communicate in isiZulu should they wish to express themselves freely.

Data analysis and interpretation

Data collected from focus group interviews were analysed using content analysis. Silverman (2000) explains that content analysis is a method of contextual investigation that involves establishing categories and then counting the number of instances when these categories are used in a specific item or text. The researcher listened to tapes, recorded in writing and read all the translated transcriptions. Struebert and Carpenter (2011), mention that data analysis begins with listening to the participant's verbal description and is followed by reading and re-reading the verbatim transcriptions of written responses. Data analysis was used for an overall sense of the data; ideas/concepts were noted as they emerged. The summaries of the interviews were made, keeping in mind that more than one theme might exist in one set of interviews. After summarising the interviews, the researcher was then able to discover themes that point to the theoretical understanding of the SBST experiences in supporting learners.

Ethical and safety issues

Participants were informed about the purpose and nature of the research, along with issues related to informed consent and confidentiality and were informed that participation is voluntary, and that they are allowed to withdraw from the research at any time without any undesirable consequences. The researcher applied for

ethical clearance from the University of Zululand's Research Ethics Committee. Ethical clearance was also received from the Provincial Research Directorate, KwaZulu-Natal, DoE. School principals provided permission to meet with and interview the participants. Participant's and schools' anonymity and privacy were protected by not using their names or any identifying details; instead codes were used. All sources used were acknowledged.

Trustworthiness was ensured by confirming credibility of the study. According to Bertram and Christiansen (2015) credibility is the extent to which the data or findings reflect the 'reality' and lived experiences of the participants and the researchers conducted voice recordings of the interviews to confirm the accuracy of the content expressed by participants. Even the fact that in-depth discussions through the use of the interview schedule were chosen as data collection method confirmed credibility. Another method of generating trustworthiness which was used was confirmability. Confirmability refers to the degree to which the analysis of the researcher can be confirmed by someone else by providing clear steps on how data was collected and analysed (Bertram, & Christiansen, 2015). Clear steps of data collection through the use of the interview schedule and transparent content analysis was implemented.

Results and Discussion

Table 2: Summary of the findings

Research objectives	Theme
OBJECTIVE 1 Experiences of SBST's	Teaching methods and curriculum differentiation.
OBJECTIVE 2 Challenges faced by SBST's	Referral to DBST Feelings of inefficiency and inadequacy Feeling of frustration over workload Lack of resources
OBJECTIVE 3 Support required by SBST	Functionality of SBST Lack of IE training Lack of support by DBST DBST process is slow Curriculum challenges Departmental policies Management support
	Parental cooperation DBST support

During data analysis, both an inductive and a deductive approach was adopted and the theoretical framework of EST was used as a conceptual tool for the interpretation of findings.

Objective 1: Investigate the experiences of SBSTs when providing support to primary schools.

Teaching methods and curriculum differentiation

Participants expressed different views based on the understanding and implementation of IE. The FSS reported successes while five other schools (S1 to S6) reported challenges in providing support to learners experiencing barriers to learning. Response from the participants indicated that IE is a good education system. All participants mentioned that their lessons are designed to accommodate all learners and they use different teaching methods and strategies when teaching learners experiencing barriers to learning. They adapt the curriculum and assessments to suit all the learners.

Participants from the FSS and mainstream schools make use of support material to try and support all learners. In their responses they indicated that:

"We are trying by all means to accommodate everyone by using different teaching strategies and curriculum differentiation. Caps allows us to adopt the curriculum and adopt the assessment as per the Screening, Identification, Assessment and Support document. Learners are being screen and

identified before they are even taught. This allows us to plan for our teaching methods and how are we going to differentiate curriculum.” (S1).

“We do apply teaching methods; however, those methods do not accommodate a diverse class. We do try our best to deliver what we can, we have never been trained on curriculum differentiation” (S1, S3, S4, S5 and S6).

Teachers understand IE, teaching strategies, differentiation of curriculum and assessment to accommodate all learners. The focus group from the FSS was the most positive attitudes about IE, perhaps because they have received more training.

Referral to DBST

The participants at two schools where the SBST is more functional mentioned that they try and intervene at a school level but, some learners require higher levels of support and are referred to the DBST for further assessment and placement at special schools. The SBSTs at these two schools meet to discuss the learners' cases and design programmes to support learners with barriers to learning. If there is no progress, learners are referred to the DBST with the relevant referral forms and the record of their interventions. The DBST needs to play an active role in supporting schools and timeously facilitate the placement of learners.

Feeling of inefficiency and inadequacy

Participants find it challenging to teach and support an inclusive class and are still struggling to understand IE. They would like to teach a diverse class once they have been capacitated like colleagues at FSS. Currently they have not even been trained on the policies related to IE.

“Our challenge is that when these learners come to our school, they are already old. They have not been supported in their previous schools. Most of them end up dropping out of school especially when they reach high schools (S6).

“I will share our experience as a Full-Service School, in some schools they do identify learners, however the challenge is with parents. They deny if you tell them that the child has a problem. Instead they will remove in that school and place them in another school, with the belief that the child will improve” (S3).

Teachers are willing to help learners but feel ill-equipped to teach learners who present with a wide variety of different challenges in the same classroom.

Feeling of frustration over workload

The participants find it frustrating, challenging and demanding to serve as SBST members and accept that teaching a diverse class is time-consuming, since it adds to their existing workloads. All participants, struggle to provide learners with individual attention, although those at the FSS felt more confident working with a diverse group of learners when compared to other groups. Participants shared their experiences:

“As a FSS our enrolment has increased since we provide moderate levels of support. The workload has increased; parents are removing learners from other schools to our schools.” (S1).

I have tried to teach them using the skills I have but I can feel that I am not coping. It is really tiring, especially that there is no(t) progress” (S3).

Teachers need support to enable them to teach a diverse class and provide relevant support. The administrative workload is another issue for schools that requires attention.

Objective 2: Challenges SBSTs face

Lack of resources

The researchers wanted to uncover challenges faced by SBSTs and all respondents expressed frustration at the lack of resources, which included financial and human. Some learners require assistive devices, like C-pen readers which can be helpful. For example, a number of learners at the schools cannot read and write however, when assessed verbally, some can provide relevant answers. Participants at all six schools pinpointed the following challenges:

“In our school the physical infrastructure is poor, to mention the few: classrooms, toilets, premises and others. The norms and standards provided by the department are not enough for us to build adapted toilets, put ramps and pave the premises” (S3).

“As a FSS we are provided with (a) budget to buy assistive devices. The department provided us with computers at the support centre and we managed to install software programmes which helps our learners with reading, mathematics and spelling. However, not all FSS have that” (S4, S5 and S6).

Functionality of the SBST

The functionality of the SBST is still a challenge in most schools because teachers struggle to understand their roles. In cases where they understand, the time factor is a challenge. It is hard for them to meet and discuss the learners' cases. Teachers feel like it's a full-time job.

“Our SBST is not functional in our school because we do not understand our role as a team. We need to be capacitated. We don't meet to discuss learner cases” (S3, S4, S5 and S6).

Functionality of the SBST is still a challenge and they need to be resuscitated so that teachers can support learners. Teachers have to also attend to other school activities like workshops, and are members of other committees, and yet learners with special needs require individual attention.

Lack of training including policies

Participants stated that they have not received training on policy-related issues, and those trained have left the school. Hence, there is a need for retraining. SBST's need to support teachers and learner with barriers to learning:

“The department did conduct some workshop around 2011/2012, however, all those who attended those workshops are no longer with us, they got promotions and some have retired.” (S2).

“As a principal I took the initiative to write to the department (SNES) section asking for (the) workshops, we have not received any positive response as yet. I feel like we are left behind” (S4).

Due to lack of capacity building and skills development teachers are unable to competently support learners experiencing barriers to learning.

Lack of support from DBST

The District is providing inadequate support; even if the DBST does conduct workshops they are too short (only for a day or two) and participants believe they require more time if they are to be adequately capacitated.

“DBST does not come to schools which is discouraging for us. They do not monitor us as SBST. It is difficult even to do the telephonic consultation because mostly you do not reach them on their phones” (S2).

“DBST is not visible, the response you get from them is that they are short staffed. I feel like they support one and the same schools like FSS and those in urban areas” (S4, S5 and S6).

DBST intervention process is slow

DBSTs take too long to attend to referrals, assessments and placements of learners. Once learners have been assessed, the policy states that they must remain at the mainstream school until placement at a FSS or resource centre (special schools) is secured.

“DBST takes time to respond to referrals. Special school waiting lists are very long, it can even take 2 years before the placement of the child is finalized. This delays the process. Sometimes learners turn 15 years whilst they are still on the waiting list for placement” (S1).

“Sometimes parents will fight with us demanding placement for their children not understanding the challenges we are facing. We sometimes advise them to visit the district offices.” (S3, S4, S5, and S6).

Difficulty accessing the DBST frustrates teachers and disadvantages learners. Learners identified by schools as requiring intervention often drop-out of school without having received appropriate support from the DBST, contributing to the country's attrition rate.

Curriculum challenges

Teachers are encouraged to adapt the curriculum and accommodate learners with special needs, but teachers are not curriculum specialists or receive training as curriculum specialists. Another challenge is specialised assessment techniques, learners with special needs struggle to read, write, follow instructions, have difficulty sitting still and may also present with behaviour challenges. Participants explain that curriculum challenges include:

“I feel like adapting the curriculum affects the self-confidence for some learners. For instance, if I group learners according to their ability, ... I feel like it affects their self-esteem and they become vulnerable to bullying” (S2).

“We need trainings on curriculum differentiation, we are struggling” (S3, S4, S5 and S6).

The SBSTs are struggling to cope and all of these challenges eventually affect the quality of teaching, learning and assessment. The SBST is meant to provide all teachers with support but the SBST do not have the necessary skills to support learners with special needs. If teachers, in the SBST, are capacitated, in terms of curriculum differentiation and assessment as per the SIAS document, they can then empower all the teachers in the school.

Departmental policies

Departmental policies expect teachers to advance learners due to age, to the next grade, who are not ready to progress. All participants at all schools have the same perspective: whenever the learner fails, a teacher has to account for their actions. The main challenge is that learners are not allowed to fail twice in a phase. National Policy pertaining to the programme and promotion requirements of National Curriculum Statement: Grades R-12. (DoE, 2013).

Objective 3: Type of support SBSTs need to improve their functionality to provide support to primary schools.

Management support

Participants mentioned that they needed the support of the SMTs to improve their functionality, but unfortunately not all participants received support from the management team.

“The participants responded that most of them are part of SMT, however, they do not receive necessary support of their principals and other SMT members. We need training so that each and every one of us understands the importance of implementing IE and understands our role” (S4, S5 and S6).

Parental support

All participants shared similar experiences with the parents of learners with barriers to learning, who mentioned that some parents are uncooperative making it difficult to assist learners. All participants from all schools expressed the need for support from parents.

“We identify learners and call the parents to schools to gather more information to assist the child, but they don’t come to school. Even if you refer children to other stakeholders like clinics, they don’t cooperate.” (S1)

“They do not assist learners with homework and do(es) not attend parents meeting to discuss learner challenges. Even if they come and they are notified about learner challenges, they deny it. This also hinders the intervention process” (S3)

The lack of parents’ cooperation makes it difficult for teachers to provide support that learners require. The DBST, SMT, SGB may all provide the necessary resources but if the parents do not the teacher is unable to follow through on the suggested interventions.

DBST Intervention

All the participants felt that they need the DBSTs support in order for them to successfully implement IE and support learners. SBSTs felt a need to be empowered by the DBST.

“DBST does not come. They only come at the beginning of the year for school functionality monitoring” (S3).

“They only come in the case of sexual abuse” (S2).

“Even if they have trained us, they must offer ongoing support and monitor and evaluate our work so that we can improve our functioning” (S4).

“Department must employ more specialist staff to help us.” (S5 and S6).

The DBST needs more specialist staff like psychologists, therapists, social workers to support learners at schools.

Overcrowding makes it difficult to provide learners with special needs with individual education plans. The large workload hinders teachers’ abilities to perform effectively and Rulwa-Mnatwana (2014) acknowledges that overcrowding may have a negative impact on learner performance. Mfuthwana and Dreyer (2018) explain

that learners with barriers to learning require specialised, individualised attention to benefit from lessons and this is not always possible in overcrowded classrooms.

The DBST, failed to support the SBSTs as much as they expected and needed. Teachers are struggling to understand and implement IE, more than two decades after the implementation of EWP6 (DoE, 2001). Mahlo and Hugo (2013) support the finding that SBST's are frustrated and helpless because there is no support and monitoring by the DBST. The DoE needs to provide schools with adequate resources to increase learner access and enhance teaching and learning. Bornman and Donohue (2014) acknowledge that one of the greatest challenges experienced by schools is the lack of resources which hinders effective teaching and learning. Thabede (2017) suggests that teacher capacity building on IE matters including policies such as Screening, Identification, Assessment and Support policy (SIAS); HIV/AIDS policy; School safety policy; Orphans and Vulnerable children policy; IE policy; Assessment policy; Health Promoting school policy and Religious policy be considered.

The SBST plays a key role in the implementation of IE. In many schools the SBST is inactive, due to number of issues: including poor understanding of their roles functions and lack of skills to support teachers. Mfuthwana and Dreyer (2018) also found that SBSTs are dysfunctional because there is lack of support from the DBST. The DBST needs to strengthen the SBST but the participants report that this has not happened. Whilst the SBST provided the platform for teachers to report about learners with barriers to learning in order to receive support, however, because of the lack of support from the DBST the SBST was unable to address the needs of teachers and learners.

Most teachers are still struggling to utilise different teaching methods and curriculum differentiation to accommodate all learners but are still unable to adapt curriculum in a manner that accommodates all learners. According to Rulwa-Mnatwana, (2014) in order for learners to reach their maximum potential, teachers need to explore different teaching strategies and adapt the curriculum. Teachers need to engage in continuous professional development and develop the necessary skills required to support learners experiencing barriers to learning.

Teachers from the FSS received training and did not encounter challenges in terms of curriculum differentiation compared to teachers from the mainstream schools. Participants from the FSS and one mainstream school were familiar with and implemented the SIAS policy, to screen and identify learners, before commencement of teaching and learning. They were also able to plan a differentiated curriculum and adapt teaching methods in advance. They also found the Learner Profile useful.

The relationship between teachers and parents has also been discouraging and Mwoma and Pillay (2016) highlight this in their study when they revealed that parents do not cooperate with teachers when they are called to school regarding education matters. Bronfenbrenner mentions that the home, as a microsystem, is one of the closest systems that provides (emotional support, academic support, a loving and caring environment) support to learners. If the microsystems (home, school, etc.) do not work together, barriers to learning are created. Stofile (2008) states that lack of support by relevant stakeholders can impact negatively on the implementation of IE and encourages teachers and parents to work collaboratively. Parents who are in denial and remove their learners from schools violate the constitution of the country which states that all children have a right to education (RSA, 1996).

Conclusion

Despite the successes in the implementation of IE in SA, there are still challenges which need to be addressed. Even if training sessions are offered by the DoE, teachers must also be encouraged to develop themselves via personal continuous professional development in order to cope with current trends and challenges within the system. One of the seven roles of the teacher is that of life-long learner.

Recommendations and limitations

The study presented with limitations, for example the sample group was delimited. This impacted on the generalizability of the study. Limitations included but are not restricted to:

- The study was conducted in only one of nine provincial districts in KwaZulu-Natal Province and one circuit in the district. SBSTs in other districts may have had different experiences. The researchers are therefore, unable to generalize the findings to other SBST in other circuits and districts.

- Only one FSS was used in the study. More participants from FSS's need to be considered for the next study of this nature.

Whilst inclusive education is a strategic policy; some gaps prevail in the implementation. It aims to address the imbalances of the past by moving away from the medical model to the social model. Even though the implementation of IE has been in existence for more than two decades now, it is proving difficult closing the gap between policy implementation and practice. This study revealed the need for further research to be conducted in the following areas:

- A comparative study can be conducted with other provinces regarding the SBSTs' experiences in providing support to their schools.
- The impact of the partnership between the department and other stakeholders in implementing IE.
- How FSS can be utilized as a resource by mainstream schools.

The SBST with a supportive management team, will perform better than members who are at a school with an unsupportive management team. The following recommendations are suggested as a result of the findings of this study. The DoE also has an active responsibility in providing adequate support to SBSTs so that they are able to efficiently effect their duties:

- conduct training workshops to equip the SBSTs with knowledge and skills to adapt the curriculum and tailor assessments for learners who experience barriers to learning
- employ more support staff so that they will be able to respond to all referrals timeously
- consider exempting SBST members from performing other duties to help ease their workload
- employing Learner Support Assistants to ease the workload especially at FSS
- request private specialists outside the department to render pro-bono specialist services
- provide financial resources so that no learner will be excluded
- build more schools to address the high ratio of learners to teacher
- employ unemployed youth with relevant qualification as teacher assistants to support schools.

The role of FSS, DBST and SBST and their potential for support are as follows:

- FSS serve as a resource for the mainstream schools as per EWP6
- DBST need to train all the schools regarding IE so that all the learners requiring high levels of support will receive an equal chance for placement
- DBST and SBST must network and share knowledge with other schools especially FSS because of the knowledge they possess
- DBST AND SBST training sessions need to be practical so that the teachers able to apply the theoretical knowledge
- DBSTs should conduct site visits to schools to provide ongoing support
- DBST needs to conduct capacity building workshops on IE for teachers so they can support learners with confidence.
- DBST is understaffed and needs to have a plan in place to reach all the schools timeously

There are other recommendations like management related issues, including policy development that are also deemed relevant and require consideration:

- SMT should provide support to teachers by organising workshops
- SMT should take an active role in supporting the SBST
- SGB to conduct advocacy sessions for parents to provide information about the importance of parental involvement
- Local and significant community leaders should assist to mobilise parents
- Schools to request donations/funding from corporate/companies to upgrade schools
- Consultation with relevant structures (DBSTs and SBSTs) to be conducted by DoE when designing policies or reviewing to check if they are still in line with current education structures.

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